

Determinants of Service Quality on Thai Passengers' Repeated Purchase of Domestic Flight Service with Thai Airways International

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Abstract : This research paper aimed to identify determinants of airline service quality on passengers' repeated purchase of service. The population of this study was Thai passengers flying domestic flights with Thai Airways, making a total of 300 samples. These 300 samples participated in this research by answering a collection of questions by means of a questionnaire. An analysis of means score and multiple regression revealed that perceived service quality for tangible elements, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy had determined repeated purchase of flight service of the passengers at a high level. Moreover, reliability and responsiveness factors could predict the passengers' repeated purchase of flight service at the percentage of 30.6. The findings gave a signal that Thai Airways may consider a development of route network and fleet strategy as well as an establishment of aircraft and seat qualification to meet passengers' needs and requirements. Passengers' level of satisfaction could also be maximized by offering service value through various kinds of special deals and programs, whereas value-added pricing strategy should be considered in order to differentiate from and beat other leading airline competitors.

Keywords : repeated purchase, service quality, domestic flight, Thai Airways

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